

Sexual promiscuity among students in tertiary institutions: Interrogating the roles of peer influence, parenting processes, social economic status and social media

SYLVESTER E. Umanhonlen ¹, ADEWUYI Habeeb Omoponle ^{2,*}, FALAYE Ajibola O. ¹, ADEGOKE S. Ayodeji ³ and Raji Naseem Akorede ⁴

¹ Department of Counselling and Human Development Studies, Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

² Department of Educational Psychology, University of Johannesburg, South Africa.

³ Department of Psychology, University of Louisiana, Lafayette, USA.

⁴ Department of Adolescent Mental Health and Well-being, Edgehill University, United Kingdom.

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Abstract

The study examined peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media as predictors of sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The study adopted the descriptive survey design of correlational type. Multi-stage sampling technique was used in this study. Data was collected using (Parental Socioeconomic Status Scale $\alpha = .89$; Parentings and Dimensions Questionnaire $\alpha = 0.79$; Peer Influence $\alpha = 0.78$; Social Network Usage Questionnaire $\alpha = .84$). Peer influence ($r = .264$; $p < 0.05$); Parenting ($r = .272$; $p < 0.05$) and social media ($r = .223$; $p < 0.05$) had a significant relationship with (sexual promiscuity) but social economic status ($r = .023$; $p < 0.05$) was not. Social media made the most significant contribution ($\beta = .156$; $t = 2.572$; $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that there is a predictive and positive relationship between peer influence, parenting, social media, and sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions.

Keywords: Peer influence; Parenting; Socioeconomic status; Social media; Sexual promiscuity; Tertiary institutions

1. Introduction

Apart from the widely publicized behavioral problems, sexual behavior is also listed among the behavioral issues prevalent among students, particularly those in higher learning institutions. The concept is described variously across literature, such as sex abuse, sex offenses, sexual promiscuity, sexual misconduct, sexual maladjustment, and sexual immorality. A sudden spike in premarital sexual activities has been noticed following acculturated customs and beliefs. Sex in Africa and Nigeria, in particular, was considered sacred and restricted only to married couples. Public opinion has consistently shown that premarital sex is perceived as dangerous and wrong, as it may serve as a precursor to abortions, teenage pregnancy, and sexually transmitted infections (Omoponle & Oyetunji, 2019).

Sexual experience among youths and adolescents may be linked to biological development, specifically the hormonal changes they experience. A regular occurrence in adolescence, especially after puberty, is activating sexual feelings (Baxter et al., 2010; Klindra, 2006). Consequently, sexuality has been widely reported to be shared among students of all categories. It is no news that many dangers are inherent in the unguided and risky sexual behavior of youths and adolescents. Ofole (2015) describes high-risk sexual behavior as those activities that potentially have adverse effects (s) on individuals' overall well-being and development. These include behaviors resulting in instantaneous physical injury and accumulating future outcomes. Some include violence, fighting, self-injury, sexual risk behaviors, use of alcohol or drugs, and reckless driving due to excess drinking.

* Corresponding author: ADEWUYI H. Omoponle; Email: adewuyihabeeb@gmail.com

While biological factors may have a significant impact on a person's sexual activity, socializing agents such as family, peers, religion, institutions, and the media can have both substantial repressive and enhancing effects on it (Noremy, Fadzilah & Mohammad, 2019; Adewuyi, 2021). Therefore, sexual behaviors are greatly influenced by societal limitations and the degree of cultural acceptance, which set the parameters for sexual practices. Contemporary youths may engage in sexual behaviors, including masturbation, homosexuality, and promiscuity, rather than non-sexual, traditional youthful activities (Dale et al., 2010). Promiscuity is a sexual perversion or reckless sexual conduct with the other gender that may be typical of adolescence, especially at puberty. According to Over and Piot (2011), promiscuity makes adolescents vulnerable to the infection of venereal diseases, including HIV/AIDS, and, more often, unwanted pregnancies. The present study examines peer influence, parenting, social-economic status, and social media as predictors of sexual promiscuity among students in tertiary institutions in Ibadan.

1.1. Peer Influence and Sexual Promiscuity

Lack of adequate sex and reproductive health education in many societies may compound young people's sexual risks and promiscuity. Moreover, many youths are socially inexperienced; therefore, they may depend on other's opinions, which makes peer pressure wield more influence on their choices and vulnerability to sexual risks (Carroll et al. 2010; Kanmodi et al. 2020). When adolescents and youths lack the necessary sexual education, they may be involved in risky sexual behaviors, making them prone to getting pregnant, having abortions, or contracting STDs. This also holds true for how peers affect sexuality, particularly sexual promiscuity. Students' preferred source of sexuality-related knowledge is their peers (Moret et al., 2016). A particularly fascinating area of study is how people perceive the actions and attitudes of their peers. A key normative predictor of intention about initiating sexual encounters and engaging in sexuality, including oral sex, is how their peers perceive their sexual practices. Peers can benefit by encouraging young people to take contraceptives, use condoms to prevent STIs, or even refrain from premarital sex (Zelalem, 2013).

Peer influence and conformity are often associated with adolescence and youth culture but strongly affect humans of all ages. In short, in the case of conformity, the group's behavior determines the individual's behavior more often than not. Dancy, Deama, and Vivek (2001), who researched peer pressure, popularity, and conformity on sexual behavior risk behavior, showed that all measures of peer conformity and popularity were correlated; peer pressure and peer conformity were strong predictors of premarital sexual risk behavior. One in every six Nigerian students admitted to partaking in premarital sex due to peer imitation (Schacht & Mulder, 2015). Additionally, Adebowale (2007) noticed significant and consistent rises in sexual behavior, primarily driven by peers' and friends' intentions. Peer norms significantly impacted the sexual attitudes and behaviors of 1,046 African-American adolescents.

Additionally, it has been discovered that their religious beliefs may influence teenagers' peer group affiliation. Many university students engage in risky sexual practices, premarital sexual activity, and prostitution because they are at an age when their sexual urge is at an all-time high. Simple observation reveals that many parents may not have taken enough time with their children. Some parents would even leave their children with guardians and other caregivers while they went on long trips. Such children may lack adequate parental supervision and care, affecting their sexual behavior (Govender & Mutinta, 2012).

1.2. Parenting and Sexual Promiscuity

In addition, many parents have in the past forced their children particularly females to work as street vendors in markets, streets, and car parks. Thereby unintentionally subjecting them to sexual harassment by older men. Unknowingly, some parents who disregard their duties to their children encourage their children to engage in early sexual activity and probably prostitution for survival's sake. The lack of communication on topics of sexual and reproductive health between adolescents and their parents is another issue that needs to be addressed. In a study of 374 parents of students in grades 7-12, Sychareun et al. (2018) found that 80% of the parents surveyed indicated that they felt the majority of sex education should occur in the home and should only be supplemented by outside sources such as the school. Most parents ranked themselves as the leading source of sexual information for their children. It is interesting to note, however, that when asked about the perceptions of other parents, only 9% of the respondents thought most parents adequately communicate with their teenage children about sexuality (Omoponle & Veronica, 2023).

Parents influence children's sexual behavior in diverse ways. For instance, their affective factors like warmth, support, antagonism, monitoring, supervision, and control influence teenage sexual behavior (Baumrind, 1987). Parental support, family cohesiveness and connection, intimate family bonds, and parent-child relationships are all associated with delayed sexual debut. Studies have found that elements of parent-child relationships, such as affection, emotional support, and discipline, are associated with delayed sexual debut. Conversely, adolescents' reports of parental rejection are related to early engagement in sexual intercourse (Price, Pound & Scott, 2014). Adolescents and young people are

likely to be free to look into their sexual preferences in an acceptable way thanks to parent-child conversations that promote positive and healthy views about sex and are founded on medically accurate knowledge (Killoren & Deutsch, 2014). Despite this, adolescents must be educated that having sex should be approached with prudence, much like most enjoyable human activities (such as eating, driving a car, etc.). When people lack appropriate information to help mitigate possible repercussions, sex may result in adverse effects. Investigations on parent-child sexual interaction have mostly ignored what parents say to their children about different sexual behavior, except for teaching them how to prevent unwanted pregnancies and STIs. Though several parents assert that they are talking to their adolescent children about sex and birth control, it is unclear precisely what they are saying. Furthermore, premarital sex is the only sexual activity that scholars who have looked into how parents talk to their adolescent kids regarding sex usually concentrate on; they have additionally evaluated the interactions in a contrasting manner, where the parents are urged to indicate whether they agree or disagree with the practice of premarital sex (Ochieng, Kakai, and Abok, 2011).

1.3. Social Media and Sexual Promiscuity

Furthermore, social media is yet another contributing component. Being the online platform with the highest growth rate in the 21st century, it is characterized by a broad range of uses, including Wikis, apps for streaming video, and social networking. For instance, with over 955 million users in 2016, Facebook users outnumbered all other social network applications, and Twitter came in second with 500 million members (Adewuyi and Jimoh, 2017). On the other side, Facebook users tend to be younger, with 300 million between the ages of 18 and 24 and 120 million between the ages of 13 and 17 of all genders. As technology has developed, mass media has become one of adolescents' most significant sources of sex-related information (Haggstrom-Nordin, 2009; Macphail & Campbell, 2011). According to a study by Kalunta-Crumpton (2017), the average Nigerian youngster had access to thousands of sexually explicit videos and other deviant behaviors. Numerous studies, both inside and outside of the lab, have discovered proof that watching television is linked to higher levels of violence or sexually risky behavior in young people. Undeniably, young people are exposed to brutality and other unlawful content through conventional media. What is worrying, however, is the fast pace at which Nigerian youth, particularly undergraduate students, are becoming dependent on new social networking platforms regardless of their adverse effects (Owan, Ekpe, & Eneje, 2020; Omoponle, 2023).

Studies have discovered strong correlations between sexual behaviors and pornography use. However, it is debatable to what extent pornography is responsible. Numerous people engage in various risk-taking activities, which could magnify any negative consequences. For instance, drinking more alcohol is linked to a higher acceptance of pornography (Godwin et al., 2012), and drinking more alcohol may enhance the harmful consequences of pornography exposure and raise the risk of sexual coercion or aggression (Figuroa-Cosme et al., 2018). The perceived confidentiality of social media may make it easier to connect with partners with more experience, which could lead to more excellent sex-related communication (Landry et al., 2014). With a broader peer network impacting their opinions and cultural standards, individuals who utilize social media frequently may engage in riskier activities. Although these results show a decline in the high-frequency use of Facebook and SMS between baseline and follow-up, this does not necessarily reflect a decline in utilization. Teenagers use recently created software programs (such as apps) that communicate within the app. We notice this due to the sudden popularity of a more recent app like Instagram (Sasson & Mesch, 2014).

1.4. Socioeconomic Status and Sexual Promiscuity

Socioeconomic status is another virulent factor when considering sexual promiscuity among students. The level of parental socioeconomic status has been linked to students' potential to engage in risky behaviors (Ramchandani, Morrison, Gold & Akers, 2018). Rodgers (2010) found that reduced sexual risk-taking behavior was connected with higher parental socioeconomic status levels. In many instances, young women who lack financial capabilities may support themselves by engaging in casual work to obtain means to cater to their needs and thus risk contacting S.T.I.s (Meekers and Calve, 2007; Okonta, 2007). For example, In South Africa, many young women engage in numerous sexual relationships in exchange for gifts, favors, and money. This may be similar to the case of some young adults in Nigeria and Cameroon (Uwakwe et al., 2014). Sutton et al. (2013) concluded that educating parents about the influence of their socioeconomic status and viable strategies to monitor their children without being intrusive is necessary. This may therefore help to ensure low-risk sexual behaviors among adolescents.

Despite the attempts by various stakeholders to reduce the challenges and effects of risky sexual behavior among young people, the situation in higher institutions does not improve, hence the need for approaches to educating individuals in practical skills to reduce sexual promiscuity. According to UNAIDS (2011), social researchers have recently realized that when developing reduction strategies for risky sexual behavior, socio-cultural factors surrounding the individual must be considered because complex health behaviors like sexual intercourse or sexual activities typically occur in context. Beyond the individual and their immediate social ties, structural and environmental factors also play a substantial effect on sexual behavior, according to Rizvi et al. (2020).

1.5. Statement of problem

Sexual promiscuity is a problem that predicts the health and well-being of individuals, families, and society. Despite worldwide concerted interventions and education about this challenge, it has increased within the last 25 years. The negative consequences of sexual promiscuity do not only play out among individuals who abuse drugs but also their families, relatives, and friends, and various institutions, government resources, and society, on the other hand.

Efforts by prior studies on causes, prevention, and treatment have seemingly yielded little or no results based on recent surveys. It appears as if these previous investigations on sexual promiscuity have raised more questions than answers. It is unclear how certain psycho-social factors, such as gender, peer influence, parental influence, attachment security, sensation seeking, self-esteem, risk-taking, and neuroticism, could predispose adolescents to sexual promiscuity. This is a gap that this study intends to fill.

1.6. Purpose of the Study

This study examines the influence of peer influence, parenting, social, economic status, and social media as predictors of sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the following are the primary purpose of the study;

- To examine the significant relationship between the independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) of sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan.
- To find out the joint effect of independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) on sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan
- To determine the relative effect of independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) on sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan.

1.7. Research Question

The following research questions guided the study:

- What is the relationship pattern between the independent variables (peer influence, parenting, social, economic status, and social media) and sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan?
- What is the joint effect of independent variables (peer influence, parenting, social, economic status, and social media) on sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan?
- What is the relative effect of independent variables (peer influence, parenting, social, economic status, and social media) on sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan?

2. Material and method

A descriptive survey research design was used for the current study. All students in Ibadan, Oyo state's higher learning institutions, comprise the study's target population. Using a multi-stage sampling procedure, the sample was drawn from the study's population. Using random sampling, the researcher selected three tertiary institutions in Oyo state. From each tertiary institution, one hundred undergraduate students were chosen randomly, giving rise to three hundred (300) students. The participants consist of both males and females.

2.1. Instrumentation

A structured questionnaire is the instrument for this study and was used to collect participant data. The questionnaire was divided into sections A and B.

2.2. Section A

2.2.1. Demographical Data

Section A collects the participants' demographic information, including the name of the institution, gender, age range, parental background, type of family, etc.

2.3. Section B

2.3.1. Parental Socioeconomic Status Scale

The parental Socioeconomic Status Scale (Salami, 2001) is a twelve-item self-report questionnaire that measures the student's socioeconomic status. This scale measures educational level, residence, parents' occupation, and types of equipment in the house. The points from the scale are further divided into three (3) parts in the scorings; high, moderate, and low socioeconomic status. The test-retest reliability of the scale was verified during the pilot study as 0.73. Scores below 15 indicate low socioeconomic status, 15-30 high, and above 30 demonstrate high socioeconomic status. The instrument has internal reliability among the sample of this study (Cronbach alpha = .89)

2.3.2. Parenting Questionnaire (PSQ)

The Parenting and Dimensions Questionnaire (P.S.Q.) was adopted to measure parenting. The P.S.Q. by Robinson et al. (2001) evaluates how adolescents view their parents' parenting. The questionnaire measures three primary parenting: authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive. The questionnaire asks for participants' perceptions of their parent's behavior. It is calculated using a 4-point scale from Strongly Agree = S.A. to Strongly Disagree = S.D. The instrument comprises fifteen items divided into three subcategories with five items each (authoritative style, authoritarian style, and permissive style). Examples include: "I can count on my parents to help me out," "My parents keep pushing me to do my best in whatever I do," and "When my parents want me to do something, they explain why." The scale is internally consistent ($\alpha = 0.79$) across various studies.

2.3.3. Peer Influence Scale (P.I.S)

Peer Influence Scale by (Steinberg and Monahan, 2007) is a 10-item scale that measures peer relationships among students. The scale was measured along a 4- Likert scales with 1= "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." Examples include "Some people go along with their friends just to keep their friends happy". It has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.78.

2.4. Social Network Usage Questionnaire

The Social Network Usage questionnaire is a 10-item measure that was adopted by Kasthuripriya (2014). Examples of items on the scale include: "What social media site do you use?", "How many social networking sites do you use," "Do you use social media through your mobile phone." Each item was rated based on the number of options. All responses recorded will be scored and averaged to indicate the social network usage level. Language validity findings of the original scale version indicated a range from .66 to .91. The scale has an internal consistency reliability coefficient of .89. However, the adapted version of the instrument was found to be reliable (Cronbach's alpha = .84) in this study.

2.5. Data Analysis

A Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was conducted to find out the relationship patterns, and Multiple Regression analysis was used to test for the joint and relative effects of the independent variables on the dependent variable on a .05 significance level.

3. Results

3.1. Research Question One

What is the relationship pattern between the independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socio-economic status, and social media) and sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan?

Table 1 Descriptive statistics and Inter-correlations among the variables

Variables	N	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
Sexual Promiscuity	300	110.00	62.23	1.00				
Peer Influence	300	60.00	38.69	0.264**	1.00			
Parenting	300	60.00	38.97	0.272**	0.919**	1.00		
Social Economic status	300	75.00	31.60	0.023	0.032	0.064	1.00	
Social Media	300	64.00	40.44	0.223**	0.301**	0.215**	0.017	1.00

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 3 shows the correlations between the independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) and the dependent variable (sexual promiscuity) among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan. It was observed that peer influence ($r = .264$; $p < 0.05$), parenting ($r = .272$; $p < 0.05$), and social media ($r = .223$; $p < 0.05$) had a significant relationship with (sexual promiscuity) among undergraduate students, but social, economic status ($r = .023$; $p < 0.05$) was found not to be substantial. Significant correlations were found among the independent variables.

3.2. Research Question Two

What is the joint effect of independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) on sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan?

Table 2 Multiple Regression Analysis on students' sexual promiscuity Data

R = .312 R Square = .098 Adjusted R Square = .084 Standard Error = 12.13650					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	4282.776	4	1070.694	7.269421	0.000
Residual	39622.275	295	147.295		
Total	43905.051	299			

*p, 0.05

From Table 4.7, it was observed that there is a significant combined effect of the independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) on the prediction of sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan. The multiple regression analysis yielded a coefficient R of .312, $p < 0.05$. The equation also showed an adjusted R^2 of .084, suggesting that the independent variables accounted for 8.4% variation in the prediction of sexual promiscuity. It was discovered that the above variances are those that this study can explain. Even if the proportion of contribution is not distributed equally, it is implied that the independent variables mentioned above made a major contribution. The remaining unexplained aspects might be elements outside the purview of this investigation.

3.3. Research Question Three

What is the relative effect of independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) on sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan?

Table 3 Relative Contribution of Independent Variables to the Prediction

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients		t	p
	B	Standard Error	β			
Constant	37.442	5.394			6.999	$P < 0.05$
Peer Influence	0.150	0.225	0.098		0.669	$P < 0.05$
Parenting	0.206	0.229	0.134		0.901	$P < 0.05$
Social Economic status	0.010	0.064	0.009		0.153	$P < 0.05$
Social Media	0.278	0.108	0.156		20.572	$P < 0.05$

Table 4.8 shows that each one of the independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) significantly contributed to the prediction of sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan. In terms of the magnitude of the contribution, social media made the most significant contribution ($\beta = .156$; $t = 2.572$; $p < 0.05$). The magnitude of the gift of other independent variables was observed in the following order: Parenting ($\beta = .134$; $t = .901$; $p < 0.05$); peer influence ($\beta = .098$; $t = .669$; $p < 0.05$); and social-economic status ($\beta = .009$; $t = .153$; $p < 0.05$).

4. Discussion of findings

4.1. Research Question One

What is the relationship pattern between the independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) and sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan? In response to the research question on the relationship pattern, the result showed correlations between the independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) and the dependent variable (sexual promiscuity) among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan. It was observed that peer influence, parenting, and social media had a significant relationship with (sexual promiscuity) among undergraduate students, but social economic status was not significant.

The study's findings are consistent with those of other studies. For instance, (Ghani, Kosnin & Aziz 2014; Harris, 2008), in their review of behavioral genetic studies, examined the impact of peer group education on adolescent behavior and concluded that approximately 50% of the variance in adolescent personality can be explained by peer influence. Best friends are one of the most potent sources of power, more powerful than friends in general, general friendship networks, or board-based peer networks, according to other studies that compared the influence of various types of peers (Berndt, 2006; Adewuyi, 2021; Chew & Eysenbach 2010; Omoponle, 2023; Awopeju et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the study's finding echoes other studies' position. For example, Abraham and Rahardjo (2015)'s study of peer group educational intervention asked participants how many friends had engaged in risky behaviors. Then it correlated the derived value with the participant's risk behavior. It was found that peer group is a significant factor predisposing participants to risky behaviors. According to Adewuyi and Muraina (2019), children are raised as good citizens most effectively when both parents live in the same household. Poor parenting denies children the ideal opportunity to acquire appropriate social behavior. Children who lack control are more likely to indulge in numerous harmful behaviors, including joining dangerous gangs and involving in anti-social behaviors (WHO, 2020; Omoponle, 2023; Ubom, 2004). Murray et al. (2019) found that family type influences the child's personality development. For example, a boy who grows up in a family where the father is not just present but also actively plays out his fatherly role would have a completely different relationship with his mother than a child who does not experience this. The relationship between the children and the mother will be considerably different when mothers are not readily available to take on their responsibilities.

4.2. Research Question Two

The second research question states, what is the joint effect of independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) on sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan? In response to the second research question on the joint contribution of the independent variables, a significant combined effect of (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) on predicting sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan. The result yielded a coefficient multiple regression R of .312, $p < .05$. The equation also showed adjusted R^2 of .084, suggesting that the independent variables accounted for 8.4% variation in the prediction of sexual promiscuity.

This aligns with the findings of Sychareun et al. (2018), who investigated the impact of female adolescents' dependence on male peers on sexual involvement. The result indicates that adolescents who depend heavily on their peers and are less involved with their families are more likely to be sexually involved, with male adolescents' dependence on male peers being a substantial factor in predicting their sexual activities. Also, Beaudoin et al. (2020) showed an increased likelihood of individuals engaging in risky behaviors if their friends do.

Evidence exists in the literature to support that adolescents' risk behaviors are associated with their close friends' behaviors. The associations may reflect friendship selection, measurement artifacts, or the operation of parallel events. Still, it is not clear whether such associations reflect peer group educational intervention. Peer group educational intervention on adolescent sexual behavior has largely been confined to the level of interaction (Wellings et al., 2019), although some studies have indicated the presence of other aspects of peer group educational intervention, e.g., harmful peer group educational intervention; this research includes peer interaction levels, intimacy, sexual behavior, and sexually risky behavior.

4.3. Research Question Three

The last research question states, what is the relative effect of independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status, and social media) on sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan? In response to the last research question on the relative effect of the independent variables, the results showed that the

independent variables (peer influence, parenting, socioeconomic status and social media) made a significant contribution to predicting sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan. In terms of the magnitude of assistance, social media made the most significant contribution. The contribution of other independent variables to marital stability was observed in the following order: Parenting, peer influence, and social economic status.

However, this finding received support from (Adewuyi, 2021; Chanakira et al., 2014, Onyemah & Omoponle, 2022) in a study involving older adolescents, which highlights alcohol-related adverse effects, like hangovers or humiliation on social media sites, and a study investigating sexually explicit material on Twitter, which offers a more instantaneous depiction of behaviors as they come up. It has consequences for surveillance and intervention in how much sex is discussed in real-time on social networks. Earlier studies in other health-related fields have demonstrated the use of Twitter to identify habits or intentions across populations. In a sample of more than 5 million tweets from individuals chosen to be geographically representative of the African people, Klindra (2006) looked for words that were alternatives for the word "sexy" in the tweets. The investigators found that tweets related to intercourse peaked between 10 p.m. and 2 a.m. in the user's local time zone and were more prevalent on Friday and Saturday nights.

Moreover, the proportion of romance-related tweets was 0.53 percent over the New Year's holiday weekend, compared with 0.34 percent during non-holiday weekends. These findings are consistent with studies emphasizing the increased risk for alcohol problems during holidays and other specific events. Thus, at the population level, the timing of tweets about sexual behaviors correlates with the times when the heaviest sexual promiscuity is known to occur (Adewuyi, 2021; Kanmodi et al., 2022; Moneto, 2010).

As an extension of the aforementioned finding, Kanmodi et al. (2020) discovered that in addition to peer sexual behavior having an adverse effect on older adolescents' sexual behavior, other peer behavior factors may also have a negative impact on adolescents' sexual behavior. Biglan et al. (2010) discovered that young people were more likely to engage in high-risk sexual behavior. Similar findings were made by Adewuyi and Yusuf (2019), who found that having a peer group with delinquent experience—defined as using alcohol, drugs, or getting into trouble- increased the likelihood of an adolescent having a sexual experience rather than being uninformed. In this same study, it was also observed that sexually experienced adolescents had higher levels of negative peer characteristics than sexually inexperienced adolescent peers' problematic behavior and substance abuse also increased the chances of the non-use of condoms among adolescents (Fagbule et al., 2021; Omoponle, 2023; Biglan et al., 2010).

5. Recommendations

To improve social competence among students of tertiary institutions, it is recommended that students should be wary of the clique they join.

Orientation programs for fresh students in higher institutions are recommended. This kind of training at the inception/resumption of study is very critical as it would equip the youths with skills needed to cope in the school and outside the school environment, mainly when issues of sexuality arise.

To educators (counselors and lecturers): they can help students to develop social interest by incorporating group or teamwork into a teaching strategy. Also, Lecturers can allow for group decision-making as a form of problem-solving ability. They can also incentivize pro-social behavior in class as a motivational tool to develop their social skills.

This study revealed the necessity for the availability of counseling services, which calls for appropriate attention. The policymakers and the government at all levels should give Counselling Services a significant position in society and make jingles that will constantly educate the nation on the importance of counseling and the challenges of sexual promiscuity among adolescents.

Educational administrators can encourage social sanctity by providing an environment that facilitates togetherness. Administrators can organize programs to unite students in the spirit of love and passion. Also, they can offer incentives at the end of the session, such as a prize given to the institution's most social and well-behaved students.

6. Conclusion

This study established a predictive and positive relationship between peer influence, parenting, social media, and sexual promiscuity among youths in tertiary institutions in Ibadan. Socioeconomic status was, however, not significant. Also, the result reveals that social media was the strongest predictor of sexual promiscuity, followed by parenting, peer

influence, and socioeconomic status. It shows that the students' social networking significantly predicts promiscuity. Also, tertiary institution students meet different categories of people in the school setting, such as peers, teachers, and others with variance degrees of sexual attitudes from different homes that model the students into sexual promiscuity.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The study's authors declare that there were no business or financial connections that may be interpreted as having a potential conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

The University of Ibadan examined and authorized the investigations that used human subjects.

Statement of informed consent

The participants' legal guardian/next of kin gave their written informed consent to participate in this study.

Availability of Data Statement

The article and supplementary materials contain the original contributions to the study; for further information, contact the corresponding author.

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